

SUSTRACK

D6.4 - FINAL EXPLOITATION AND SUSTAINABILITY PLAN

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Authors	Gabor Mester, Ema Gustafikova (PC)
Reviewers	All partners

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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Nature of the deliverable:	R*
Dissemination Level	
PU	Public, fully open, e.g. web
CL	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC
CO	Confidential to SUSTRACK project and Commission Services

* R: Document, report (excluding the periodic and final reports)

DEM: Demonstrator, pilot, prototype, plan designs

DEC: Websites, patents filing, press & media actions, videos, etc.

OTHER: Software, technical diagram, etc.

SUSTRACK Consortium:

#	Participant Organization Name	Short Name	Country
1	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA UNITELMA SAPIENZA	UNIT	IT
2	STICHTING WAGENINGEN RESEARCH	WR	NL
3	KNOWLEDGE SRL	KE	IT
4	PEDAL CONSULTING SRO	PC	SK
5	DBFZ DEUTSCHES BIOMASSEFORSCHUNGSZENTRUM GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	DBFZ	DE
6	UNIVERSITEIT GENT	UGENT	BE
7	FUNDACION TECNALIA RESEARCH & INNOVATION	TECNALIA	ES
8	FVA SAS DI LOUIS FERRINI & C	FVA	IT
9	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI FERRARA	UNIFE	IT
10	BUNDESANSTALT FUER MATERIALFORSCHUNG UND - PRUEFUNG	BAM	DE
11	FUNDACION CIRCE CENTRO DE INVESTIGACION DE RECURSOS Y CONSUMOS ENERGETICOS	CIRCE	ES

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In the context of the SUSTRACK project, the management of innovation and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) has been a central element for ensuring that project results can be effectively exploited and sustained beyond the project's lifetime. From the beginning, the consortium applied a structured strategy and methodology for IPR management, aligning innovation activities with the overarching objective of supporting Europe's transition from linear, fossil-based systems to sustainable circular and bio-based alternatives.

This deliverable constitutes the Final Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (ESP) of SUSTRACK. It provides a comprehensive account of the consortium's approach to IPR and innovation management, detailing the methodology applied, the assets identified, and the strategies developed for their protection and exploitation. The report presents the final portfolio of Key Exploitable Results (KERs) and outlines concrete exploitation pathways, target groups, protection measures, and partner-level commitments to ensure long-term uptake and impact.

The final ESP is the concluding version of this plan, following the Initial Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D6.3, submitted in M6). Building on this earlier iteration, it now consolidates the definitive exploitation strategies, including individual and asset-based plans, and provides evidence of the consortium's actions to strengthen exploitation readiness.

By integrating these elements, the final ESP sets out a clear roadmap for sustaining and valorising SUSTRACK's outputs beyond the project duration. It demonstrates how the results will continue to inform policy processes, support research and innovation, foster industrial transformation, and contribute to societal transitions towards a circular bioeconomy in line with the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan.

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List of Abbreviations	
Abbreviation/Acronym	Description
BG	Background
CA	Consortium Agreement
CSA	Coordination and Support Action
EC	European Commission
EM	Exploitation Manager
EPC	European Patent Convention
ER	Exploitable Results
ESP	Final Exploitation and Sustainability
EU	European Union
FG	Foreground
GA	Grant Agreement
IP	Intellectual Property
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
KERs	Key Exploitable Results
MML	Mobilisation and Mutual Learning
PC	Project Coordinator
PMC	Project Management Committee
PR	Project Result
R&D	Research and Development
SMEs	Small and Medium-sized Enterprises
WBS	Work Breakdown Structure
WIPO	World Intellectual Property Organisation
WP	Work Package

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Purpose and Scope

The SUSTRACK consortium has consistently focused on generating results that remain sustainable beyond the project's completion. From the early stages, partners have worked to ensure that innovative ideas, methodologies, and knowledge outputs are fully identified, preserved, and made available to relevant stakeholders. To this end, the consortium established clear principles and a robust management framework for both Background (BG) and Foreground (FG) Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), thereby enabling structured protection and effective use of assets.

The ESP has served as the guiding instrument for monitoring the protection and valorisation of intellectual assets throughout the project's lifecycle. This final version consolidates the work initiated in the Initial Exploitation and Sustainability Plan (D6.3, M6) and its subsequent update presents the definitive portfolio of SUSTRACK's exploitable assets. It also defines the agreed exploitation routes, the associated IPR arrangements, and the long-term sustainability strategies.

By doing so, the ESP ensures that the results of SUSTRACK will continue to create value through policy, industrial innovation, research, and societal transitions, thereby facilitating successful uptake, replication, and deployment beyond the project's duration.

1.2 Document structure

The final version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan has the following structure:

- **Chapter 1** provides introductory information about the context in which this report has been elaborated as well as its targets and structure.
- **Chapter 2** clarifies the key terms pertaining to the IPR management of the project, defines the underlying objectives and explains the main intellectual property protection instruments to be employed.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the IPR management strategy and its underlying stages in the context of SUSTRACK and describes the methodology that was followed in this respect.
- **Chapter 4** introduces the IPR Matrix and explains the procedures followed to identify the SUSTRACK background and foreground IP, as perceived at the conclusion of the project.
- **Chapter 5** offers an overview of the project's assets, as well as the background and foreground IPs as perceived by all SUSTRACK partners.
- **Chapter 6** presents exploitation plans per assets
- **Chapter 7** introduces individual exploitation plans

- **Chapter 8** describes briefly how innovation management is articulated in SUSTRACK and how the relevant stakeholders interact with the innovation management process along with the lessons learnt.
- **Chapter 9** presents the Stakeholder Adaptation approach
- **Chapter 10** concludes with the next steps towards the exploitation of the assets of the project.

1.3 Summary of main updates

The final version consolidates the project's work on innovation and IPR management, presenting a complete and validated portfolio of KERs and the definitive strategies for their long-term exploitation.

Compared to earlier versions, this deliverable introduces:

- **A finalised list of KERs**, clearly defining their ownership, contributing partners, intended users, and protection measures.
- **Refined exploitation routes** at both the asset and partner level, demonstrating how results will be applied in policy, research, industry, and civil society contexts.
- **Concrete commitments from partners** outlining how SUSTRACK results will be integrated into their institutional strategies and sustained beyond the project lifetime.
- **Updated IPR Matrix**, capturing the complete set of Background (BG) and Foreground (FG) IP, together with the confirmed access rights and protection strategies.
- **Sustainability measures and legacy pathways**, including mechanisms for maintaining assets through networks, repositories, and stakeholder platforms.
- **Alignment with EU priorities**, positioning SUSTRACK outputs in the context of the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and the Sustainable Development Goals.
- **Reflections on lessons learned** during the exploitation process, providing guidance for future projects.
- **Stakeholder Adaptation Roadmap**, providing guidance on how different groups (EU/national policymakers, industry actors, researchers, and civil society organisations) can integrate SUSTRACK results into their practices, policies, and strategies.

Through these updates, the final ESP provides a consolidated, forward-looking strategy that ensures SUSTRACK's results remain accessible, exploitable, and impactful beyond the project's conclusion.

2. IPR MANAGEMENT OVERVIEW

2.1 Objectives

The objectives of SUSTRACK's ESP reflect the need to protect and valorise all project assets, to ensure efficient management of outcomes generated throughout the project, and to enable their wide availability and uptake by relevant stakeholders. The plan also provides the framework for sustaining and deploying SUSTRACK's exploitable results after the completion of the project.

Accordingly, the main objectives of the SUSTRACK ESP are to:

- **Define and agree on the IPR management methodology** applied within SUSTRACK.
- **Identify and consolidate the project's assets**, creating a portfolio of KERs generated during the project lifecycle.
- **Develop a shared understanding** among partners concerning the Background (BG) and Foreground (FG) intellectual property and the associated access rights.
- **Determine appropriate protection measures** for each identified exploitable result.
- **Prevent or resolve potential conflicts** related to IP management within the consortium or in relation to external stakeholders.
- **Establish guiding principles** and common actions to ensure the smooth implementation of IPR strategies across the consortium.
- **Promote stakeholder adaptation** and long-term uptake by developing tailored strategies and roadmaps that enable policymakers, industry, researchers, and civil society actors to integrate SUSTRACK results into their practices and policies.

The ESP defines how the following elements were managed in the context of SUSTRACK, thereby creating a clear pathway for post-project exploitation and sustainability:

- Background IP
- Foreground IP
- Exploitable Results / Key Exploitable Results (KERs)
- Access Rights
- Protection of Results
- Dissemination and exploitation measures
- Stakeholder adaptation and sustainability roadmaps

These key concepts are consistent with Horizon Europe guidelines for exploitation and sustainability planning. Their definitions are provided in the following section and have been validated and agreed upon by all SUSTRACK partners.

Definitions

2.1.1 Background IP

Background IP can be defined as data, know-how or information - including any rights - owned or licensed to a project partner prior to the commencement of the agreement and needed to implement the action or exploit the project's assets.¹ The background needed for carrying out the project activities or exploiting the underlying results must be accessible to the other project partners on a royalty-free basis. Under this frame, all project partners must identify the background as pertinent to the project actions and grant access rights to this IP.² The background of a project can be identified and agreed:

- (i) Within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, or
- (ii) in a separate agreement ("agreement on the background").

In this respect, there are two main aspects to consider when dealing with the background of a project:³

- **Identification of background:** Naming of the assets that each project partner provides to the consortium, and which are imperative for the successful implementation and exploitation of the project actions.
- **Definition of Access Rights:** Clarification of the rights to use knowledge under the terms and conditions agreed within the consortium and alignment with the underlying background rules and obligations set by the EC to ensure the smooth implementation of the project.

2.1.2 Foreground IP

Foreground refers to the results and assets that are generated through the implementation of project activities, including pieces of information, materials, and knowledge.⁴ These results comprise any tangible or intangible output of the project's actions which can be protectable or not. In this respect, foreground IP can arise and be obtained from project partners to protect and

¹ See Article 16 of the SUSTRACK Grant Agreement

² See Attachment 1 in the Consortium Agreement for a detailed description of the SUSTRACK background and the access rights granted.

³ European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al., *European IP Helpdesk : successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe : boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>. Last accessed: 6/10/2025.

⁴ For a detailed definition of the Foreground see: <https://iprhelphdesk.eu/glossary/foreground>. Last accessed: 6/10/2025.

exploit the underlying exploitable results of the project. It includes intellectual property rights (e.g. copyrights, industrial designs, patents), similar forms of protection (e.g. rights for databases) and unprotected know-how (e.g. confidential material). It should be noted that results generated outside the project activities cannot be defined as foreground.

SUSTRACK's Grant Agreement (GA) establishes that the results of the project are owned by the project partner who generates them.⁵ Due to the collaborative nature of SUSTRACK, certain results have been jointly developed by multiple partners. In such cases, joint ownership may arise among the contributing partners and are governed by mutual agreement on the allocation of rights and the conditions under which joint ownership is exercised. Although regulations concerning the frame of joint ownership are embedded in the SUSTRACK GA,⁶ it would be best practice for partners to establish during the project implementation a separate joint ownership agreement to define the allocation and terms of exercising their ownership. Each joint owner can grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties to exploit the joint-owned results unless otherwise agreed in the CA or the joint ownership agreement.

2.1.3 Exploitable Results

The exploitation of project results means the utilisation of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned (e.g. in other research activities; or in developing, creating and marketing a product or process; or in creating and providing a service, or in standardisation activities).⁷ Under this scheme, an **exploitable result** is defined as a project result (expected or achieved) that meets the following two conditions:

- Has commercial/social/academic relevance;
- Can be commercialised/exploited as a standalone result (e.g. product, process, service, etc.).⁸

Therefore, exploitable results can be a combination or part of a foreground result(s). Not all foreground items may meet the above conditions.⁹ Furthermore, exploitable results are not necessarily market-ready; they may require further R&D, engineering and validation before becoming commercially exploitable.

⁵ See article 16 of the SUSTRACK Grant Agreement, Annex 5

⁶ See article 16 of the SUSTRACK Grant Agreement, Annex 5

⁷ European Commission, Glossary, Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>, Last accessed: 6/10/2025.

⁸ A patent for licensing is also an exploitable result.

⁹ European Commission, Communication, Dissemination And Exploitation Why They All Matter And What Is The Difference?, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf, Last accessed: 6/10/2025.

2.1.4 Access Rights

Access rights refer to one partner's rights for requesting access to another project partner's background and foreground to implement its activities under the project or to use its own results. Additionally, access rights can be used if they are needed for exploiting the project's results. The provisions governing access rights within a collaborative Horizon Europe project follow specific rules pre-defined in the GA and the CA. Access rights within SUSTRACK are presented in Table 1.

Table 1 Access Rights

Purpose of access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Project implementation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royalty-free Unless otherwise agreed by participants 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Royalty-free
Exploitation of Own results	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Subject to individual agreement Granted under fair and reasonable conditions 	

2.1.5 Protection of Results

It should be noted that when considering IP protection, IP assets can be protected by several types of IPR, and therefore, the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The choice of the most appropriate form of intellectual property (IP) protection is determined by the nature and specific characteristics of the result, as well as by the strategic objectives of its owner.

There are various types of instruments that may be considered for protecting IP. Under the framework of SUSTRACK, meaningful IP protection instruments that can be used are the following:

- Trade and service marks;
- Patents;
- Utility models;
- Copyrights;
- Trade secrets;
- Confidentiality agreements.

Further details about each of the above-mentioned protection instruments are provided in the subsections below.

Trademarks and service marks

Trademarks

A trademark constitutes an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered.¹⁰ Trademarks consist of signs capable of distinguishing the products (either goods or services) of a trader from those of others. The main function of a trademark is to identify the commercial origin of a product. This does not mean that it should inform the consumer of the actual person who has manufactured the product or even the one who is trading in it. It is sufficient that consumers can trust in a given enterprise, not necessarily known to them, being responsible for the product sold under the trademark.

Service Marks

In modern trade, consumers are confronted not only with a vast choice of goods of all kinds but also with an increasing variety of services which tend more and more to be offered on a national and international scale. There is therefore a need for signs that enable consumers to distinguish between different services such as insurance companies, car rental firms, airlines, etc. These signs are called service marks and fulfil essentially the same origin-indicating and distinguishing function for services as trademarks do for goods. Since service marks are signs which are very similar in nature to trademarks, the same criteria could be applied. Thus, service mark protection has sometimes been introduced by a very short amendment to the existing trademark law or simply by providing for the protection of service marks under the provisions of the trademark law.¹¹

Patents

A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) that offer a new technical solution or facilitate a new way of doing something. The patent holder has the exclusive right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting their invention for a limited period. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application.¹²

The patent owner has the right to decide who may or may not use the patented invention throughout the period during which the invention is protected. Additionally, the patent owner may give permission to other parties, or permit them, to use the invention on mutually agreed terms. The owner may also sell the right to the invention to someone, who then becomes the new owner of the patent. Finally, patents are granted only country by country, some regionally (e.g. European), and may also be used in non-patented territories (although in such cases they would not enjoy the patent protection). Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and the invention becomes part of the public domain, meaning that owners do not hold exclusive rights any longer. Therefore, it becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others.¹³

¹⁰ For the definition of trademark in Europe, see: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ddf8fb93-ec0e-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> Last Accessed: 6/10/2025.

¹¹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law, and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 68f.

¹² Definition of patents in the European context retrieved from: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ddf8fb93-ec0e-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> Last accessed: 6/10/2025.

¹³ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 17.

Utility Models

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorisation, for a limited period.¹⁴ The inclusion of utility models into the intellectual property system in some countries has the primary objective of nurturing the rapid evolution of indigenous innovativeness, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises and among individuals.¹⁵

Copyrights

Copyright (or author’s right) is the term used to describe the economic and moral rights that creators have over their literary, scientific and artistic works. It is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original.¹⁶ There is exhaustive list containing the works that can be protected by copyright. However, there are several works usually covered by copyright at an international level:¹⁷

- Literary works such as novels, poems, plays, newspaper articles;
- Computer programmes, databases;
- Films, musical compositions, and choreographies;
- Artistic works such as paintings, drawings, etc; and
- Advertisements, maps, and technical drawings.

Copyright protection also includes moral rights, including the right to claim authorship of a work, and the right to oppose changes to it that could harm the creator’s reputation. The creator - or the owner of the copyright in a work - can enforce rights administratively and in the courts, by inspection of premises for evidence of production or possession of illegally made “pirated” goods related to protecting works. The owner may obtain court orders to stop such activities, as well as seek damages for loss of financial rewards and recognition.

Trade Secrets

Any confidential business information that provides a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. The type of information that could be protected as a trade secret is

¹⁴ Definition of utility models in the European context retrieved from: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ddf8fb93-ec0e-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> Last accessed: 6/10/2025.

¹⁵ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁶ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁷ Definition of copyrights in the European context retrieved from <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/ddf8fb93-ec0e-11e9-9c4e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en> Last accessed:6/10/2025.

therefore highly diverse. It could include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes or manufacturing processes.¹⁸

Confidentiality Agreements

Confidentiality is an extremely important issue for participants in innovation projects, from the setting-up stage to the implementation and exploitation phases. Exchanging valuable information with other partners is generally a necessity that regularly occurs in collaborative initiatives or undertakings. Accordingly, confidentiality issues and measures should be taken into consideration to safely exchange information, facilitate the project development and ensure the non-disclosure of sensitive technology, business or commercially confidential information. Confidentiality agreements provide protection and security to an organisation that is about to share or make available information to another organisation by ensuring that confidential information will be used only for the permitted purposes agreed between the signatories of the agreement and will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent. Therefore, the signature of a confidentiality agreement could be a very important step to keep confidential information secret in order to maintain a competitive edge.¹⁹

There are specific criteria to determine a confidentiality agreement as legally enforceable:

- The information must be secret, i.e. not readily accessible to people who normally deal with this kind of information;
- It must have commercial value;
- The owner must have taken reasonable steps to protect it.

¹⁸ Definition of trade secrets in the European context retrieved from <https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>, Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

¹⁹ See confidentiality agreements on the WIPO website: https://www.wipo.int/sme/en/documents/disclosing_inf_fulltext.html. Last accessed: 13/4/2023.

3. APPROACH

Throughout the SUSTRACK project, the management of intellectual property (IP), exploitation, and sustainability has been guided by a common framework designed to ensure clarity and consistency across the consortium. This framework has been built on shared principles concerning Background and Foreground knowledge, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, as well as the balance between dissemination and exploitation during and after the project.

The ESP applies a comprehensive approach that structures IP management into three distinct stages:

- **Grant Agreement preparation stage** - defining background knowledge, initial access rights, and preliminary exploitation intentions;
- **Project implementation stage** - identifying, protecting, and managing Foreground results and KERs, while ensuring alignment between dissemination and exploitation activities;
- **Post-project stage** - safeguarding sustainability through partner commitments, stakeholder uptake, and long-term exploitation pathways.

Figure 1 below provides an overview of the IPR management stages as applied in SUSTRACK, illustrating the continuum from preparation to implementation and post-project sustainability. Importantly, this final version of the plan consolidates the lessons learned during the project and confirms the consortium's shared commitments to maintaining and exploiting SUSTRACK's results beyond its lifetime.

Figure 1 IPR Management stages

3.1 Preparation Stage

Both the GA and the CA contain provisions governing various aspects of intellectual property rights. These documents serve as the primary reference framework for all IPR matters within the consortium. Accordingly, any further measures or actions related to IPR undertaken by project partners were implemented in alignment with, and supported by, the provisions established therein.

3.1.1 Grant Agreement (GA)

The GA constitutes the central contract between the European Commission and the SUSTRACK consortium, establishing the key rules and conditions governing the project. It serves as the primary contractual basis for SUSTRACK and includes specific provisions on IPR under **Article 16: “Intellectual property rights – background and results – access rights and rights of use.”** Within this framework, the management of SUSTRACK’s intellectual property is regulated, including the definition of access rights and obligations related to background knowledge. Furthermore, the GA sets out the principles for ownership and protection of results generated by the project, as well as their exploitation and dissemination. Finally, it regulates the transferability of rights and establishes access conditions to ensure the effective use of SUSTRACK’s outputs.

3.1.2 Consortium Agreement (CA)

The CA is the internal contract among the SUSTRACK partners, defining their mutual rights and obligations for the implementation of the project’s activities. It provides a framework for collaboration, minimises the risk of disputes, and establishes clear rules regarding responsibilities and access rights. In particular, it regulates the rights and responsibilities of consortium members concerning intellectual property, ensuring transparency and consistency throughout the project.

The key provisions of the SUSTRACK CA referring to IPR are contained in the following sections:

- Section 8 - Results: sets out provisions on ownership and joint ownership of results, as well as conditions for their transfer and dissemination.
- Section 9 - Access Rights: defines the principles governing access rights, including those required for exploitation and dissemination.
- Attachment 1 - Background included: presents the initial list of usable background knowledge contributed by the partners.

Together, these provisions complement the GA by providing a detailed and operational framework for managing intellectual property within the consortium.

3.2 Implementation Stage

During the implementation of SUSTRACK, dedicated procedures for IP management were applied across the consortium to ensure the effective organisation and monitoring of results and assets. As the project progressed, particular emphasis was placed on the identification of Foreground results, the clarification of ownership and access rights, and the establishment of appropriate protection measures. In parallel, exploitation pathways were defined to support the valorisation and, where relevant, the commercialisation of SUSTRACK's outputs.

The IPR management framework adopted by SUSTRACK provided robust and transparent procedures for addressing issues of strategic importance, thereby enabling the consortium to maximise the exploitation potential of its results and to secure their long-term sustainability beyond the project's duration.

Therefore, partners focused on two different points:

- **Providing access rights to their knowledge for other partners to carry out their work on the project.**
- **Establishing early asset identification procedures to protect, disseminate and exploit the project's assets.**

In this respect, key IP-related issues in the SUSTRACK implementation phase included:

- **Background Identification**
- **Foreground Identification**
- **Results' ownership**
- **Protection of results**
- **Exploitation of results**
- **Dissemination of results**

This final ESP consolidates these procedures and confirms the partners' joint commitments to ensure that SUSTRACK's outputs remain accessible, exploitable, and impactful well beyond the project's lifetime.

3.2.1 Background Identification

In the early stages of SUSTRACK, it was essential to identify the relevant knowledge, know-how, and partner data that constituted the project's background. Within this framework, the defined background could be linked to the assets generated during implementation, thereby facilitating the determination of access rights, ownership arrangements, and intellectual property provisions.

3.2.2 Foreground Identification

A core element of SUSTRACK's IP management has been the systematic identification of project assets to establish a comprehensive mapping of results and strengthen the SUSTRACK IP portfolio. All assets of IP value have therefore been identified, listed, named, described, and analysed in a structured manner, ensuring clarity of ownership, protection needs, and exploitation potential.

3.2.3 Results' ownership

Partners have been asked (through the SUSTRACK IPR Matrix) to elaborate further on the provisions of the CA regarding the results' ownership. Special attention was paid to handling joint ownership issues.

3.2.4 Protection of results

Effective exploitation of the innovative concepts and assets developed under the frame of SUSTRACK depends on the protection of the project's results. In particular, the project's results must adequately be protected if:²⁰

- The project's results can reasonably be expected to be commercially exploited and;
- Protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (given the circumstances).

On this note, **when considering IP protection, SUSTRACK partners must consider their own interests along with the interests of the consortium.** Project partners should safeguard the identified exploitable SUSTRACK results with adequate protection schemes, which will offer a protection period within a suitable geographical territory. The geographical territory should be agreed upon by the parties in advance, based on where the IP will be used. By default, Europe is considered to be the suitable territory in which the identified exploitable SUSTRACK results will be safeguarded, but it remains at the discretion of the interested parties to collectively reach an agreement regarding this matter.

Table 2 illustrates a list of different protection instruments. The ones most applicable to the SUSTRACK project are highlighted, as considering the CSA nature of the project, it is not expected to employ all the instruments in the list.

²⁰ See: <https://cms.eurice.eu/storage/uploads/news/files/lp-management-in-collab-horizon-projects.pdf>, Last accessed: 6/10/2025.

Table 2 Indicative list of protection instruments

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Invention	X	X			X
Software ²¹	X	X	X		X
Scientific Article			X		
Technology Design			X	X	
Name of Technology				X	
Know How	X	X			X
Website			X	X	

IP protection constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale or commercialisation of IP in the form of products and services. IP utilisation is vital for prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it could contribute to supporting the branding of products and services both to customers and investors. It should be noted that the IP protection of an asset is not always mandatory.

3.2.5 Exploitation of results

The identified exploitable results and assets of SUSTRACK were effectively exploited relevant use as foreseen during the SUSTRACK project. In particular, the SUSTRACK consortium sought exploitation opportunities of the project's results in:

- i) Further research activities;
- ii) Creating and providing a service;

3.2.6 Dissemination of results

SUSTRACK partners have committed to selecting the most appropriate channels for the dissemination of project results (e.g. scientific publications, dedicated websites, conferences, open-access repositories), in accordance with the provisions of the CA²² and any specific confidentiality arrangements. In line with Horizon Europe principles, partners were required to ensure that adequate protection measures are applied to exploitable results prior to any dissemination activity, thereby safeguarding intellectual property while enabling broad visibility and uptake of the project's outcomes.

3.3 Post project Stage

At the formal conclusion of the project (M36), the consortium submitted the ESP (D6.4), which represents the definitive account of SUSTRACK's exploitation, and sustainability strategy. This

²¹ Software patentability is still a debated issue given its exclusion as subject matter as by Article 52(2)(c) and (3) of the European Patent Convention (EPC). Source: IPR Helpdesk.

²² See Section 8.4 of the SUSTRACK Consortium Agreement.

deliverable provides the final outline of how the consortium commits to utilise its exploitable Foreground results, including their consolidated descriptions, identified sectors of application, and the related plans and timelines for exploitation.

The ESP also details the full range of activities undertaken and planned to deploy SUSTRACK's achievements, covering both dissemination and exploitation pathways as well as measures designed to secure the long-term sustainability of results. A particular focus is placed on the integration of results into policy, research, industry, and civil society contexts, ensuring their continued relevance and impact beyond the project's lifetime.

In addition, the deliverable incorporates the final findings on IP management, including the updated IPR Matrix. This matrix presents a comprehensive overview of all applied and registered rights, access arrangements, and ownership structures, providing a transparent record of how IP has been managed within the project.

Finally, the ESP presents the advanced strategy for exploitation and sustainability, consolidating concrete partner-level commitments. This strategy ensures that SUSTRACK's KERs are positioned for effective uptake, replication, and upscaling, thereby safeguarding the project's legacy and reinforcing its contribution to the European Green Deal and the transition towards a sustainable circular bioeconomy.

3.4 Role of the Exploitation Manager

The **Exploitation Manager (EM)** was responsible for leading the definition and implementation of SUSTRACK's ESP. This role encompassed the preparation of the relevant reports, the systematic assessment of innovative ideas emerging during the project for their exploitation potential, and the proper management of all Background, Foreground, and intellectual property assets.

To this end, the EM (PEDAL) has worked in close coordination with the Project Coordinator (UNIT) and the Project Management Committee (PMC) to ensure the optimal handling of all IP assets and the coherent application of SUSTRACK's IPR strategy. The EM and the Project Coordinator have jointly overseen organisational and managerial aspects of IPR implementation. As part of good practice, all partners were encouraged to inform and consult the EM and the Coordinator prior to deciding on protection measures for results arising from their activities—particularly where potential joint ownership of IP may apply.

Beyond these core responsibilities, the EM has actively **facilitated individual exploitation activities** by organising dedicated discussions with each partner. These bilateral exchanges provided targeted guidance, addressed partner-specific needs, and supported the alignment of individual exploitation plans with the overall project strategy. In addition, the EM has explored options for **platforms to deploy SUSTRACK findings** for integration.

To reinforce the external visibility and sustainability of SUSTRACK's outcomes, PEDAL will further carry out the following targeted activities as Exploitation Manager:

- **Submit results to the EU Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (ECESP):** Create a dedicated “Publication” entry based on SUSTRACK’s policy recommendations and Monitoring Tool ([ECESP](#)).
- **Feed the Monitoring Tool into the Bioeconomy Knowledge Centre:** Engage with the JRC Bioeconomy Unit to present SUSTRACK indicators and the Monitoring Tool ([Knowledge4Policy - Bioeconomy](#)).
- **Present findings at EU Circular Economy Industry Platforms:** Target industry alliances and networks including the [Circular Plastics Alliance](#) , the [Construction 2050 Alliance](#) , and the [Textile Exchange](#).
- **Publish methods and tools in open repositories:** Deposit results, methods, and tools in open-access repositories such as [ZENODO](#).
- **Add the SUSTRACK Monitoring Tool to the EU Innovation Radar:** Showcase the tool within the Innovation Radar platform ([Innovation Radar](#)).

Finally, the EM acts as a mediator in the event of IP-related conflicts (see Section 3.6), monitored exploitation-related activities across the consortium, and continuously contributed to the development of updated versions of the ESP.

3.5 Knowledge Management of the project

The management of IP has been an integral part of the overall SUSTRACK project management structure, with permanent IP monitoring established throughout the project’s implementation. From the early stages, an efficient IPR management methodology was applied to define the procedures for handling newly generated or identified results during the project’s lifecycle.

Effective IP management in SUSTRACK has been ensured by adopting a systematic process for identifying IP-relevant results, determining appropriate protection measures, and guiding their exploitation. To guarantee that IP information was captured reliably and in a timely manner, clear mechanisms were established: whenever Work Package Leaders identified a new asset arising from their activities, the EM was promptly informed.

The EM, in close cooperation with the Coordinator and the partners responsible for generating the asset, has been responsible for screening and managing newly identified results and their associated IP issues. Based on the nature of the asset and the objectives of SUSTRACK, the EM has directed partners towards the most suitable and efficient IPR strategy to be applied.

To support this process, the IPR Matrix was designed as a living tool within the ESP. This matrix has been continuously updated and expanded to include newly generated Foreground results and assets, thereby ensuring that all relevant outputs are systematically captured, assessed, and positioned for exploitation and sustainability.

3.6 IP Conflicts

To proactively avoid IP conflicts, project partners were well-informed about IP rules and guided through the exploitation process not only via the IPR Matrix but also through the help of the EM and prepared guidelines too. In this respect, project partners were identifying their IPR assets, formulate their ownership and exploitation claims and if deemed necessary, transfer any relevant results to SUSTRACK's exploitable results according to the principle rights and obligations defined in the CA of the project.²³

The EM helped with the following indicative (and not exclusive) aspects:

- If there was a possible misunderstanding about the definition of the exploitable result and therefore of the object of claims?
- If there were any exploitation claims that had to be further specified so that the partners can check the compatibility of their claims?
- If there were any exploitation claims compatible with the ownership claims of the partners (related issue of access rights)?
- If there were any confidentiality issues e.g. on new knowledge of strategic importance for a partner and consequently the need for a confidential agreement?
- If there were any possible IP conflicts between the partners, both related to ownership and the related need for access rights and exploitation claims?

Importantly, throughout the implementation phase of SUSTRACK, no IP-related conflicts emerged within the consortium. This reflects both the clarity of the agreed IPR framework (as defined in the GA, CA and in D6.3) and the constructive collaboration among partners in addressing ownership, access rights, and protection issues.

²³ See Section 8 of the SUSTRACK Consortium Agreement.

4. IPR MATRIX METHODOLOGY

The IPR Matrix was used in the framework of the project to define the main IPR issues related to the Exploitation and Sustainability strategy. This approach facilitated the consortium partners to identify the background, foreground, and exploitable results. In addition, the IP protection measures, and the necessary agreements were defined to ensure the successful exploitation of the project outcomes even after the completion of the project.

The IPR methodology follows four (4) interconnected steps:

1. **Identification of the Background IP** and definition of the access rights of the consortium partners
2. **Identification of the Foreground IP** that was produced in the framework of the project's activities.
3. **Identification of the Exploitable assets/results** that were produced in the framework of the project.
4. **Definition of the IPR protection** of the identified exploitable assets/results that can be potentially exploited by the consortium partners.

During the implementation period of SUSTRACK, the ESP primarily focused on defining the project's key assets and, to the extent possible, identifying the Background (BG) and Foreground (FG) intellectual property (IP) together with their corresponding access rights. As the project advanced and concludes, the IPR methodology was progressively refined to capture and integrate the evolving set of results and their associated management requirements.

By the later stages of implementation, the identification of exploitable assets required the establishment of clear ownership arrangements among the consortium partners for each KER. In parallel, rules and conditions for access to these results were defined, ensuring both adequate protection and effective pathways for exploitation. The validation of IPR arrangements was applied rigorously, safeguarding the consortium's assets while enabling dissemination and sustainability.

Within this framework, the IPR Matrix has functioned as a living tool throughout the project, continuously updated to reflect newly generated results and their associated ownership, access, and protection measures. The final structure of the IPR Matrix is presented in Table 3.

Table 3 Structure of the IPR Matrix

Background (BG)	Foreground (FG)	Exploitable results (ER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BG# • Partner’s Background • Contributing Partner • Short Description of BG • Type of Protection • How will it be utilised within SUSTRACK? • Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK • Conditions to use outside SUSTRACK • Interest in further exploitation through SUSTRACK results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • FG# • Project Outcome /Achievement/Result • Related WP • Contributing Partners • Short Description of FG • Related BG# (BG owner) • Type of Protection • Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK • Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results • Conditions to Use after the end of the Project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ER# • Exploitable result • Main partner • Further contributing partner(s) • Related FG# • Related project task/deliverable (if applicable) • Related BG# (BG owner) • Proposition for the ER-owner • Short description of the ER • Relevance for IP Protection

4.1 Identification of Background IP

As first step, the Background of the project was identified.

Multiple information regarding the Background IP is recorded in the respective template. In the second column of the table, a short name of the Background is given. Then, the responsible partner is mentioned, and a number is assigned related to the Work package and the number of assets. In the 5th column of the table, a short more detailed description of the BG is offered. Furthermore, the partners define the Type of protection in terms of patents, utility models, copyrights, trade and service marks, trade secrets, creative commons licenses, and confidentiality agreements, among others. In column seven (7), the partners define how this BG will be used in the framework of the project, and then in columns eight (8) and nine (9) describe the conditions under which the consortium partners and the stakeholders outside the consortium respectively can use the BG. Finally, the partners state their interest in further exploitation of the BG in the framework of the project through the produced results. (Table 4).

Table 4 IPR Matrix Background Template

#	Relevant Background (the name of the Background)	Contributing Partner	BG identifier	Short description of BG	Type of protection (e.g., patent, copyright, TM, Utility model)	Conditions to use within SUSTRACK (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA..)	Conditions to use outside SUSTRACK E.g. Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes on what conditions?	Interest in further exploitation through SUSTRACK's results (Yes/ No)
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The background IP was registered by the project partners by M36, as perceived at the conclusion of the project. The results are presented in the next chapter.

4.2 Identification of Foreground IP

Partners have identified the Foreground that was produced during the project's activities.

The template was used by the consortium partners to identify the foreground IP. In the first four columns, the SUSTRACK project achievements are listed along with the respective WP. Then, the main contributing partner is mentioned. Usually, if an FG comes as a direct result of a Task, then the main partner is the Task leader. In addition, the rest of the contributing partners are also mentioned. Similarly, the contributing partners are usually the partners contributing to the Task that the FG emerges from. In the 7th column, the number of the related Background IP is mentioned while in column eight (8) is given a short description of the FG. Furthermore, a Foreground number is assigned to the respective FG. Similarly, to the background identification template, the partners also define the type of protection, the conditions under which the FG can be used by the consortium partners and the interest for the commercialisation through the project results. Finally, in the last column, the conditions (e.g., free to use, license fee, etc.) to use after the end of the project was indicated by the project partners (Table 5).

Table 5 IPR Matrix Foreground Template

WP	#	Project result (PR)/ Achievement	Specific project result	Main Partner(s)	Contributing partner(s)	Related BG number	Short description of FG	FG number	Type of protection (e.g., patent, copyright, TM, Utility model, CC licence)	Conditions to use within SUSTRACK (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA...)	Interest in Further Commercialisation of Project Results (Yes/ No)	Conditions to use after the end of project (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA...)
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The identified Foreground IP up until M36 can be found in the respective chapter.

4.3 Identification of exploitable results

In the third stage and based on the identified FG the consortium partners defined the exploitable results and the IPR management procedures:

- i) Protection
- ii) Definition of access rights
- iii) Exploitation pathways

The main aim of this third stage of the IPR Matrix where the exploitable results and the main contributors were defined was:

- To identify IP ownership and exploitation claims, as well as pro-actively indicate possible conflicts for each exploitable result; and
- To support decisions on issues pertaining to IP protection, to timely make the needed steps in this regard, including any potential IP agreements (e.g. for joint ownership, providing access rights or even an NDA for confidentiality).

Table 6 was used throughout the whole duration of the project to deploy the third stage of the IPR Matrix and identify the exploitable results.

Table 6 IPR Matrix Exploitable Results Template

ER#	Exploitable Result	Short description of ER	Main partner	Contributing Partner(s)	Related FG	Related BG	ER Owner(s)	Potential IP protection	M	U	L	S	O	(which exploitation path is most promising)
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In the first three columns, the number, a short name and a brief description of the exploitable results were mentioned. In the next two columns, the main responsible partner and the rest contributing partners were listed. In columns 6th and 7th, the number of the related FG and BG was indicated. In addition, in the next column, the proposed owner of the exploitable result was defined, while in column nine (9) the relevance for IP protection was indicated by the responsible partner. The next five (5) columns indicate the five (5) different categories of exploitation claims.

- **M:** Making a product and selling it.
- **U:** Using the project result internally for further development, for instance:
 - To develop something else for sale; or
 - For R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research projects.
- **L:** Licensing the project result to third parties.
- **S:** Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc.
- **O:** Others

The partner responsible for the exploitable results with the support of the contributing partners, the coordinator and the exploitation manager choose which exploitation claims best fit the ER. In the final column, the most promising exploitation claim was indicated.

5. OVERVIEW OF SUSTRACK'S ASSETS, BACKGROUND AND FOREGROUND IP

5.1 Identified Assets of SUSTRACK

Table 7 presents the identified assets and their short description as defined by the consortium partners at the conclusion of the project.

Table 7 Identified Assets

No.	Asset	Description	Main Partner(s) Responsible
1	WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios	8 of these scenarios have been carried out (two per sector) and involved the collection and review of the current and prospective policy goals that might influence the sustainable transition at the EU, country (and possibly regional) levels. Data was based on the screening of policy documents, expert consultations, and verification via stakeholder workshops.	DBFZ
2	Policy recommendations and guidelines	These were produced for each case study summarising the findings for each of the carbon intensive sectors and providing indications of pressing actions and sustainability considerations to support the sustainable transition at the national and EU levels. These were the main output of T5.3	DBFZ
3	Case studies analyses Textile Sector	Textiles sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.	WR
4	Case studies analyses Construction sector	The building sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.	UGENT
5	Case studies analyses Biochemical sector	The biochemical sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the	WR

No.	Asset	Description	Main Partner(s) Responsible
		framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.	
6	Case studies analyses Bioplastics sector	The bioplastics sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.	BAM
7	WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities (including capacity building for local stakeholders; tools and methodologies)	These capacity-building activities were carried out to strengthen the knowledge base and practical know-how of local stakeholders during DEPLOY workshops, enabling them to engage meaningfully in transition processes. They supported the contextual analysis of potential transition pathways, taking into account geographical, social, and cultural specificities. Building on the outputs of policy scenario development and modelling (WP4, Task 4.3), together with the identification of local policy priorities, the activities equipped stakeholders with the tools to define concrete, actionable steps along the most appropriate transition pathway for their context. At the same time, they enabled stakeholders to anticipate and address potential pitfalls while leveraging opportunities within their respective sectors (construction, chemicals, textiles, and plastics) and national frameworks.	PEDAL
8	WP6 Co-creation activities (including 3 international conferences (EU level), 6 national conferences and 3 mutual learning workshops)	Three EU-level conferences were organised to support partners in task-related stakeholder activities (e.g., co-creation), with the primary objective of sharing the knowledge, tools, and models developed by SUSTRACK, while jointly creating stakeholder-oriented content and solutions. In parallel, six national conferences were held to fine-tune the SUSTRACK approach through localised validation activities and to co-develop policy recommendations at both sectoral and country levels. These national DEPLOY conferences also empowered stakeholders by providing targeted capacity-building activities (Tasks 4.3 and 5.2). Furthermore, two Multi-Actor Mutual Learning (MML) workshops were implemented: the first (M3)	PEDAL

No.	Asset	Description	Main Partner(s) Responsible
		engaged with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives to exchange methodologies, lessons, and early findings, while the second (M30) served to refine SUSTRACK's results and recommendations, thereby maximising the exploitation potential and long-term uptake of the project outcomes.	
9	Reports and deliverables	All project activities were accounted for through the publication of the project results through the project reports and deliverables	UNIT
10	Event format package	Innovative formats (live, online, hybrid) of collaboration and stakeholder engagement with enhanced interactive applications and tools, in the context of INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences as well as MMLs with other projects and initiatives and final event.	FVA
11	Toolkits / Actionable knowledge	Package of actionable knowledge ready to be exploited by target stakeholders (e.g., researchers, industries, policy makers, civil society), including factsheets, videos, infographics, toolkits, capacity building materials.	All Partners
12	Monitoring and assessment framework	This consists in guidance for decision-makers that explains the approach of monitoring and assessing the transition towards bio-based circular economy	TEC
13	Monitoring and assessment dashboard	This consists in a ready-to-use tool to map outcomes of the assessment of bio-based circular systems as described in the monitoring framework	TEC
14	Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring	A joint document, elaborated as result of the workshop "Projects4Future" organised by SUSTRACK and EuBioNet, aggregating policy recommendations from several projects (ARGONAUT, BioFairNet, BioINSouth, BIOTRANSFORM, CheMatSustain, COPilot, ESCIB, INNOVATE-EU, Pilots4U, ShapingBio, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, SYMBA, and 3-CO). The document was submitted to the European Commission's public consultation for the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy ("Towards a circular, regenerative and competitive bioeconomy").	FVA
15	Working group on "Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring" under EuBioNet	SUSTRACK enabled the creation of the working group on "Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring" under the EuBioNet (managed by FVA). During the project, trusted relations among projects dealing with those topics have been initiated and consolidated, also through a number of MML activities, also resulting in the production of a joint document collecting aggregated policy recommendations delivered to inform the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy.	FVA

5.2 Background

The project partners identified the Background (BG) intellectual property required to achieve the objectives of SUSTRACK. The consolidated list of Background assets made available for use within the project is presented in **Annex 1**.

5.3 Foreground IP

The identification of the Foreground (FG) intellectual property has been completed and is presented in **Annex 2**, which provides the consolidated overview of SUSTRACK's generated assets. This final version captures all results, know-how, and exploitable outputs produced during the project, together with their associated ownership, access rights, and protection measures. As such, Annex 2 represents the definitive reference for the exploitation and sustainability of SUSTRACK's Foreground results beyond the project's lifetime.

6. EXPLOITATION PLANS PER ASSET

This section presents the main assets of the SUSTRACK project, together with the principal contributors to their development. For each asset, details are provided on the intended users, the benefits expected from its exploitation, and the potential routes for uptake and deployment.

In addition, the main creators of each asset have outlined the foreseeable actions required to enable the chosen exploitation pathway(s), specifying what needs to be done, by whom, and within which timeframe.

To ensure clarity, the information is structured into two tables for each asset:

- A table summarising the exploitation plan of the asset.
- A table summarising the required actions to facilitate its exploitation.

Each asset is described in a dedicated sub-section below, providing a comprehensive overview of SUSTRACK's portfolio of exploitable results and the steps foreseen to secure their sustainability beyond the project's lifetime.

6.1 WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios

The exploitation plan for WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios is presented in Table 8.

Table 8 Exploitation plan for WP3 Policy portfolio scenarios

Asset description	8 of these scenarios have been carried out (two per sector) and involved the collection and review of the current and prospective policy goals that might influence the sustainable transition at the EU, country (and possibly regional) levels. Data was based on the screening of policy documents, expert consultations, and verification via stakeholder workshops.
Creators of Asset	DBFZ, UNIT, BAM, WR, TEC, KE, UNIFE, PEDAL, UGENT
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Policy makers: An overview of the current policy instruments impacting the case studies supports to adapt and develop these further; overview of opportunities for policy instruments to integrate and support a sustainable transition to a circular bioeconomy. Industrial players: Overview of actual and prospective policy instruments can have impacts on their business cases. Civil society: Overview of policy instruments influencing the sector and what policy instruments could support the development of the sector. General interest from civil society exists. Modellers: the scenario settings (assumptions) can be implemented in further models and in this way the assumptions of the policy landscape of a sustainable transition.

Intended exploitation route	Further dissemination through communication channels such as social media outlets is planned through visual media that will invite key stakeholders to visit SUSTRACK repository of results .
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The actions needed for the exploitation of the Policy Portfolio Scenarios are presented in Table 9.

Table 9 Actions needed for the exploitation of the Policy Portfolio Scenarios

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of Policy portfolio scenarios. Share scenarios/roadmaps with ministries, EC services, and regional authorities. Internal sharing with the DBFZ community of the scenario results has been carried out. Will integrate scenarios into ongoing research and policy support Evidence of uptake: presented at EC policy workshops; cited in stakeholder events	DBFZ and partners involved in the scenario development and workshop	After the final report (M36)

6.2 Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines

The exploitation plan for Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines is presented in Table 10.

Table 10 Exploitation plan for Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines

Asset description	These were produced for each case study summarising the findings for each of the carbon intensive sectors and providing indications of pressing actions and sustainability considerations to support the sustainable transition at the national and EU levels. These will be the main output of T5.3
Creators of Asset	DBFZ, UNIT, WR, BAM, TECNALIA, PC, FVA, KE
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Policy makers: An overview of the current policy instruments impacting the case studies support to adapt and develop these further + overview of opportunities for policy instruments to integrate and support a sustainable

	transition to a circular bioeconomy. Industrial players: Overview of prospective policy instruments that could be implemented in the future and have impacts on their business cases Civil society: Overview of policy instruments influencing the sector + what policy instruments could support the development of the sector.
Intended exploitation route	The path towards exploitation was by way of the IMPLEMENT conference (M28) co-creation workshop and presented to selected regional, national and EU policy makers in six policy roundtable discussions in the partners’ respective countries, in the context of the DEPLOY conferences (M30-M34). A copy of the recommendations was produced and published on the resources tab on the project website. Let alone being highly disseminated through the project’s social media channels and Zenodo repository.

The actions needed for the exploitation of Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines are presented in Table 11.

Table 11 Actions needed for the exploitation of Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of results. Promote SUSTRACK policy recommendations in EU/national policy dialogues. The DBFZ has used insights collected during our work in SUSTRACK and in particular in the WP5 to provide comments to the EU Commission on the planned EU Circular Economy Act. Committing to promoting recommendations in policy advocacy and networks. Evidence of uptake: Endorsed during stakeholder consultations; shared with national ministries.	All SUSTRACK Partners	After the final report (M36)

6.3 Case studies analyses TEXTILE sector

The exploitation plan for Case Study analyses for textile sector is presented in Table 12.

Table 12 Exploitation plan for Case Study analyses TEXTILE SECTOR

Asset description	Textiles sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.
Creators of Asset	WR, UNIT, TECNALIA
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	All Stakeholders. Overview of challenges and solutions to address them both in terms of economic, policy and sustainability transition needs. Both recommendations for monitoring needs and for policy instruments were made.
Intended exploitation route	This was achieved through capacity building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the preparation for these capacity building activities were made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for Case Study analyses for the textile sector are presented in Table 13.

Table 13 Actions needed for Case Study analyses for TEXTILE SECTOR

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of results. Use in academic publications, sectoral roadmaps, and industrial workshops Evidence of uptake: Referenced in industrial association meetings and academic conferences	All SUSTRACK Partners especially WR, UNIT, TECNALIA	After the final report (M36)

6.4 Case studies analyses CONSTRUCTION sector

The exploitation plan for Case Study analyses for the construction sector is presented in Table 14.

Table 14 Exploitation plan for Case Study analyses CONSTRUCTION SECTOR

Asset description	The building sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.
Creators of Asset	UGENT, WR
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	All Stakeholders. Overview of challenges and solutions to address them both in terms of economic, policy and sustainability transition needs. Both recommendations for monitoring needs and for policy instruments were made.
Intended exploitation route	This was achieved through capacity building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the preparation for these capacity building activities were made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for Case Study analyses for the construction sector are presented in Table 15.

Table 15 Actions needed for Case Study analyses for CONSTRUCTION SECTOR

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of results. Use in academic publications, sectoral roadmaps, and industrial workshops Evidence of uptake: Referenced in industrial association meetings and academic conferences	All SUSTRACK Partners especially WR, UNIT, TECNALIA	After the final report (M36)

6.5 Case studies analyses BIOCHEMICAL sector

The exploitation plan for Case Study analyses for the biochemical sector is presented in Table 16.

Table 16 Exploitation plan for Case Study analyses for BIOCHEMICAL SECTOR

Asset description	The biochemical sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.
Creators of Asset	WR, DBFZ
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	All Stakeholders. Overview of challenges and solutions to address them both in terms of economic, policy and sustainability transition needs. Both recommendations for monitoring needs and for policy instruments were made.
Intended exploitation route	This was achieved through capacity building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the preparation for these capacity building activities were made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for Case Study analyses for the biochemical sector are presented in Table 17.

Table 17 Actions needed for Case Study analyses for BIOCHEMICAL SECTOR

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of results. Use in academic publications, sectoral roadmaps, and industrial workshops Evidence of uptake: Referenced in industrial association meetings and academic conferences	All SUSTRACK Partners especially WR, DBFZ	After the final report (M36)

6.6 Case studies analyses BIOPLASTIC sector

The exploitation plan for Case Study analyses for the bioplastics sector is presented in Table 18.

Table 18 Exploitation plan for Case Study analyses

Asset description	The bioplastics sector is facing critical challenges within the current linear system. It was tested whether the proposed monitoring system works, to identify necessary changes/improvements to the framework. The analysis of the final findings also contributed to the macro scenarios generated in WP4 and allowed for the definition of overarching policies in WP5. Outcomes were validated during the IMPLEMENT workshops with the sectoral experts.
Creators of Asset	BAM, WR
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	All Stakeholders. Overview of challenges and solutions to address them both in terms of economic, policy and sustainability transition needs. Both recommendations for monitoring needs and for policy instruments were made.
Intended exploitation route	This was achieved through capacity building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the preparation for these capacity building activities were made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for Case Study analyses for bioplastics sector are presented in Table 19.

Table 19 Actions needed for Case Study analyses for the BIOPLASTICS SECTOR

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination	Dissemination of results. Use in academic publications, sectoral roadmaps, and industrial workshops Evidence of uptake: Referenced in industrial association meetings and academic conferences	All SUSTRACK Partners especially BAM	After the final report (M36)

6.7 WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities

The exploitation plan for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities is presented in Table 20.

Table 20 Exploitation plan for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities

Asset description	These capacity-building activities took place to boost the know - how of local stakeholders in each respective partner country and to analyse the implementation of the potential transition paths, based on their contextual specificities (e.g., geographical, social, cultural). The results of the policy scenario development and modelling (WP4, T4.3) and the identification of local policy priorities enable stakeholders to identify actionable steps along the most suitable transition pathway while identifying the pitfalls and opportunities of this pathway in the respective sector (i.e., construction, chemical, textile or plastic sector) and country.
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	ALL stakeholders: Those engaged from each case study, and technical experts for the utilisation of the assessment toolkit prepared in WP2 and capacity-building material from WP4 (Modelling). Multi-actors from case studies: 1. Conclusion and recommendations for each bio-based sector. 2. Guidelines for the identification and review of case study information and results from the environmental, social and economic assessments. Technical experts in each country (participating in the project and/or where a case study has been selected): 1. Dashboard to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition and learn how to apply it. 2. Receiving prepared learning materials (e.g. model tutorials) for the forecast of transition pathways.
Intended exploitation route	This was achieved through capacity-building seminars organized alongside the DEPLOY (6 national conferences). These were held in Italy UNIT/FVA; Spain-TECNALIA/CIRCE; Germany BAM/DBFZ; Slovakia-PC; Netherlands-WR and Belgium-UGENT. Moreover, the tools and methodologies in the build-up to these capacity-building activities will be made available to other projects and stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities are presented in Table 21.

Table 21 Actions needed for WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Deploy Conferences, Dissemination	Dissemination of results. Adoption of methodologies by partners in future	Partners organising the DEPLOY national conferences as well as owners of the capacity-building materials	During the DEPLOY Conference (M30 - M34) 4 Online seminars (M28 -

	capacity-building. Evidence of uptake: applied methodologies in stakeholder workshops across multiple countries		M32). After the final report (M36)
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6.8 WP6 Co-creation activities

The exploitation plan for WP6 Co-creation activities is presented in Table 22.

Table 22 Exploitation plan for WP6 Co-creation activities

Asset description	Three EU-level conferences were organised to support partners in task-related stakeholder activities (e.g., co-creation), with the primary objective of sharing the knowledge, tools, and models developed by SUSTRACK, while jointly creating stakeholder-oriented content and solutions. In parallel, six national conferences were held to fine-tune the SUSTRACK approach through localised validation activities and to co-develop policy recommendations at both sectoral and country levels. These national DEPLOY conferences also empowered stakeholders by providing targeted capacity-building activities (Tasks 4.3 and 5.2). Furthermore, two Multi-Actor Mutual Learning (MML) workshops were implemented: the first (M3) engaged with relevant EU-funded projects and initiatives to exchange methodologies, lessons, and early findings, while the second (M30) served to refine SUSTRACK’s results and recommendations, thereby maximising the exploitation potential and long-term uptake of the project outcomes.
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	ALL stakeholders. Results of co-creation activities.
Intended exploitation route	The major output from these activities was the creation of actionable knowledge which will then be disseminated through the project’s established channels. All these results are referenced and shared through the resources tab on the project website and are available to the wider stakeholder community and the general public during and after the project.

The actions needed for WP6 Co-creation activities are presented in Table 23.

Table 23 Actions needed for WP6 Co-creation activities

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Co-creation activities at INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences	Disseminate the methodology to relevant stakeholders, have it open access. Replication of formats in EU projects and policy platforms. Evidence of uptake: Formats replicated in clustering events and stakeholder dialogues	All Partners	During and after the end of the project (M36).

6.9 Reports and deliverables

The exploitation plan for reports and deliverables is presented in Table 24.

Table 24 Exploitation plan for reports and deliverables

Asset description	All project activities are accounted for through the publication of the project results through the project reports and deliverables
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	ALL stakeholders. Sharing knowledge with all stakeholders regarding project results and activities.
Intended exploitation route	Public deliverables were published on the project website and made available to the wider stakeholder community and the general public during and after the project via the SUSTRACK Community profile on Zenodo.

The actions needed for reports and deliverables are presented in Table 25.

Table 25 Actions needed for reports and deliverables

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Disseminate the overall results to the stakeholders and have them open access. Long-term use via EU repositories and academic channels. Evidence of uptake: Deliverables downloaded via project website and ZENODO; cited in publications	All Partners, PEDAL	During and after the end of the project (M36).

6.10 Event format package

The exploitation plan for Event format package is presented in Table 26.

Table 26 Exploitation plan for Event format package

Asset description	Innovative formats (live, online, hybrid) of collaboration and stakeholder engagement with enhanced interactive applications and tools, in the context of INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences as well as MMLs with other projects and initiatives and final event.
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Projects, academia, research, policymakers or other stakeholders organising events such as co-creation workshops, MMLs, and roundtables. Free access to a methodology and guidelines for designing and implementing Mobilisation and Mutual Learning Workshop, co-creation workshops, and roundtables. Sharing knowledge with all stakeholders regarding project results and activities.
Intended exploitation route	Public deliverables are published on the project website and made available to the wider stakeholder community and the general public during and after the project.

The actions needed for event format package are presented in Table 27.

Table 27 Actions needed for event format package

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Disseminate the overall results to the stakeholders, have them open access. Evidence of uptake: Deliverables downloaded via project website and ZENODO; cited in publications	All Partners	During and after the end of the project (M36)

6.11 Scenario simulations generated using the Green Economy Model

The exploitation plan for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model is presented in Table 28.

Table 28 Exploitation plan for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model

Asset description	There are a baseline and policy scenarios available for exploitation and further analysis. The data generated from the scenarios are shared and made accessible for further processing if required.
Creators of Asset	All Partners
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	All stakeholders: Projects, academia, research, policy makers or other stakeholders organising events such as co-creation workshops, MMLs, roundtables Improved insight into the systemic nature of policy action on key socioeconomic and environmental indicators, estimate of the cost of transition: For KE: model structure and data is used for other projects such as the work with Climate Vulnerability Forum (CVF) and the Climate Prosperity Plans (CPPs), and the the Global Circular Economy modelling with UNEP.
Intended exploitation route	The report describes both the methodological approach as well as an interpretation of results, which increases the understanding of the systemic nature of biobased practices; Additionally, the model structure is open source and replicable and can therefore be used in other projects.

The actions needed for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model are presented in Table 29.

Table 29 Actions needed for Scenario simulations generated using Green Economy Model

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Dissemination of report (methodology and findings); Evidence of uptake: use of model structure and data.	All Partners	After reports were produced; after the end of the project (M36); Once the model structure was completed.

6.12 Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring

The exploitation plan for Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring is presented in Table 30.

Table 30 Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring

Asset description	A joint document, elaborated as result of the workshop "Projects4Future" organised by SUSTRACK and EuBioNet, aggregating policy recommendations from several projects (ARGONAUT, BioFairNet, BioINSouth, BIOTRANSFORM, CheMatSustain, COPilot, ESCIB, INNOVATE-EU, Pilots4U, ShapingBio, STAR4BBS, SUSTCERT4BIOBASED, SYMBA, and 3-CO). The document was submitted to the European Commission's public consultation for the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy ("Towards a circular, regenerative and competitive bioeconomy").
Creators of Asset	All Partners especially FVA.
Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Policy makers and decision makers (public and private sector). One-stop shop of aggregated policy recommendations stemming from several projects, initiatives and stakeholders.
Intended exploitation route	Submitted to inform the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy Policy recommendations made available to stakeholders via the project website to facilitate easy replicability.

The actions needed for Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring are presented in Table 31.

Table 31 Actions needed for Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Submission to the public consultation. ²⁴ As well as presentations of the main outcomes on 13 May 2025, at the BIOBASEDCERT Cluster Final Event in Brussels. Evidence for uptake: Page visits and downloads.	All Partners	Before and after the end of the project (M36)

6.13 Working group on “Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring” under EuBioNet

The exploitation plan for Working group on “Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring” under EuBioNet is presented in Table 32.

Table 32 Exploitation plan for Working group on “Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring” under EuBioNet

Asset description	SUSTRACK enabled the creation of the working group on “Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring” under the EuBioNet (managed by FVA). During the project, trusted relations among projects dealing with those topics have been initiated and consolidated, also through a number of MML activities, also resulting in the production of a joint document collecting aggregated policy recommendations delivered to inform the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy.
Creators of Asset	All Partners especially FVA.

²⁴ https://ec.europa.eu/info/law/better-regulation/have-your-say/initiatives/14555-Towards-a-circular-regenerative-and-competitive-bioeconomy/F3566517_enWebsite

Intended users and expected benefits from exploiting the asset	Other projects and initiatives, policy makers and decision makers. Facilitate dialogue, debate, mutual learning and production of aggregated outputs.
Intended exploitation route	Maintenance of the working group under EuBioNet beyond the end of SUSTRACK.

The actions needed for Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring are presented in Table 33.

Table 33 Actions needed for Aggregated policy recommendations on standardisation, certification, labelling and monitoring

Action	What?	By whom?	When?
Dissemination activities	Organisation of future events involving the working group. Evidence for uptake: Existence of the working group and organisation of future events involving projects under it.	FVA	Before and after the end of the project M36)

7. EXPLOITATION PLANS PER PARTNER

This section provides a summary, in **Table 34**, of the SUSTRACK assets that each partner has identified as their primary exploitation interests, together with the planned approaches and actions they intend to pursue to realise these opportunities. These commitments demonstrate the consortium's concrete plans for ensuring the post-project exploitation, replication, and long-term sustainability of SUSTRACK's results.

Table 34 Individual Exploitation Plans

UNIT	Results of major interest:
	<p>Along with the project management activities undertaken during the SUSTRACK project, UNIT has already shared some overall results on several platforms, at conferences, and in stakeholder events at both European and national levels. Additionally, the outputs from WP1 have been published as scientific papers led by UNIT. The identification of policy instruments to support the transition is of major relevance for UNIT. Therefore, UNIT will continue to promote policy recommendations at the EU and national levels to facilitate science-based communication on the design of sustainable routes towards circular bio-based systems via sharing recommendations and roadmaps with ministries, EC services, and regional authorities.</p> <p>Building upon the acquired knowledge and experience in project management, UNIT will take part in developing new project proposals to expand and/or replicate SUSTRACK results. Moreover, regarding the stakeholder empowerment activities, UNIT developed close collaboration opportunities with other Horizon Europe projects and bioeconomy clusters at the EU and national levels. UNIT will continue to use its wide network to provide knowledge on the best approaches and methodologies for the sustainable transition.</p>
WR	Results of major interest:
	<p>For WR results of major interest are a further elaboration of approaches (indicators, metrics and models) to monitor circularity at biobased product level and at system level. In addition WR is interested in identifying best policy instruments to stimulate the transition to a more circular and sustainable bioeconomy. The knowledge generated in the project will be used for scientific publications, acquire new EU projects and provide services to policy makers and companies active in innovations for more circular production systems.</p> <p>The main exploitable results of interest are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 2 - Policy recommendations and roadmap 3 - Case study textiles 4 - Case study building sector 5 - Case study biochemicals 6 - Case study bioplastics

13 - Monitoring framework	
PC	Results of major interest: Reports and deliverables, WP5 Stakeholder empowerment activities, WP6 Co-creation activities, Policy recommendations and Roadmap guidelines
<p>PEDAL, as SUSTRACK’s Exploitation Manager will integrate the project’s results and assets into its established consulting and advisory portfolio. By embedding SUSTRACK’s policy recommendations, methodological frameworks, and monitoring tools into its advisory services, PEDAL will enhance its capacity to deliver evidence-based guidance to both private and public sector clients.</p> <p>Beyond enriching its existing services, PEDAL will also leverage the new collaborations and networks established during SUSTRACK—including connections with policy makers, industry stakeholders, and civil society organisations—to expand its client base and extend its market reach. By systematically applying SUSTRACK’s outputs in advisory assignments, PEDAL will support clients in adopting sustainable transition pathways, aligning strategies with EU policy frameworks (e.g., the European Green Deal and the Circular Economy Action Plan), and improving their long-term competitiveness.</p> <p>In this way, PEDAL ensures that the exploitation of SUSTRACK’s results will have a direct and lasting impact, both by consolidating its own service offer and by amplifying the systemic reach of the project’s outcomes across European and international contexts.</p>	
DBFZ	Results of major interest:
<p>For DBFZ results of major interest are policy scenarios, policy modelling results and final policy recommendations / action plan. The knowledge created and synthesised here will be used for subsequent publications and policy advice services provided by DBFZ to national and EU policy makers.</p> <p>The DBFZ has used insights collected during our work in SUSTRACK and in particular in the WP5 to provide comments to the EU Commission on the planned EU Circular Economy Act.</p> <p>Share scenarios/roadmaps with ministries, EC services, and regional authorities. Internal sharing with the DBFZ community of the scenario results has been carried out. Likewise, further dissemination through our communication channels such as social media outlets is planned through visual media that will invite key stakeholders to visit SUSTRACK repositories of results.</p> <p>A scientific publication with results of WP5, in particular the design of policy factsheets with a portfolio of policy instruments and derived policy recommendations after consultations with stakeholders is planned. DBFZ will use methodologies as input in future Horizon Europe proposal and keeping SUSTRACK outputs visible on websites, repositories, and networks.</p>	
FVA	Results of major interest:
<p>The FVA team will integrate innovative formats (live, online, hybrid)/tools/methodologies of collaboration and stakeholder engagement developed in the context of co-creation and stakeholder empowerment activities in its existing engagement practices in different fields (e.g., bioeconomy and circular economy, ocean and waters protection), in order to better support</p>	

future EU funded projects and initiatives and maximize stakeholder engagement, collaboration among projects, science-to-policy interfaces, and, consequently, their impact across Europe.

Moreover, FVA, in its role of ecosystem facilitator, gained substantial knowledge, methodologies and tools for monitoring the transition, as well as expert stakeholders' contacts, which will be exploited in future projects to expand and/or replicate SUSTRACK results as well as to empower stakeholders at local/regional, national and European levels.

Moreover, regarding the collaboration with other projects and initiatives, SUSTRACK enabled the creation of the working group on "Standardisation, Certification, Labelling, and Monitoring" under the EuBioNet (managed by FVA). During the project, trusted relations among projects dealing with those topics have been initiated and consolidated, also through a number of MML activities, also resulting in the production of a joint document collecting aggregated policy recommendations delivered to inform the revision of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy. This working group will continue after the end of the SUSTRACK project.

BAM	Results of major interest: Deliverables (reports), papers and internal stakeholder activities at BAM
BAM researchers were responsible for preparing different reports that were represent the basis for scientific publications. In addition, the results will be disseminated internally at the BAM community in at least three internal dissemination events (including presenting posters at BAM events).	
Unife	Results of major interest:
UNIFE researchers will use the results produced by SUSTRACK for the preparation of several scientific reports and publications. In addition, the results may be taken into consideration for the development of further design activities.	
CIRCE	Results of major interest:
CIRCE researchers have used the AHP methodology to test its potential in the different sectors covered by the project, checking how useful it can be to support decision-making. They have also contributed with their knowledge to tasks and deliverables related to the standard CWA 17898:2022, exploring how it can help connect the project results with international references. This experience opens the door to future uses, such as certification, monitoring, or evaluating sustainability practices, both in public and private projects, and the results will also be taken into account for future scientific publications.	
TECNALIA	Results of major interest:
For TECNALIA, results of major interest are:	
The development of a monitoring tool providing	
i) Access to Data & Indicators - It facilitates access to existing resources, including key indicators and datasets that track the progress of the bioeconomy transition	

<p>ii) Intuitive Performance Assessment - It offers a user-friendly evaluation of country performance across critical management areas, such as environmental impacts, competitiveness and jobs, sustainable resource use, and the role of bio-based renewable resources.</p> <p>Results from the assessment of cross-sectoral policy impacts for portfolio scenarios.</p> <p>These key outcomes will help TECNALIA in consolidating its capacities for developing tailored services towards territorial clusters interested in transitioning towards circular systemic solutions at local level</p>	
KE	Results of major interest:
<p>For KE, the work performed in Sustrack is already being exploited for other projects. The data and model structure developed has been picked up in the GEM-CPP model developed under the Climate vulnerability forum (CVF), the structure and data has been inserted into the Global-GEM model used in the project “Mapping Macroeconomic Impacts: A modelling framework for Circular Economy pathways”. The CVF works on country reports, so the work is published when countries express interests. The UNEP work will be published in February 2026.</p>	

The information presented in **Table 34** was collected through structured partner inputs and bilateral discussions facilitated by the EM. To ensure consistency, partners completed an **Exploitation Assessment Template**, which guided them in identifying the assets of greatest relevance to their exploitation strategy, describing their intended use, and outlining the concrete steps foreseen to realise these opportunities. The consolidated overview reflects the consortium’s shared commitment to sustaining and deploying Sustrack’s results beyond the project’s duration.

8. INNOVATION MANAGEMENT STRATEGY

This section outlines how innovation management has been articulated in SUSTRACK and how relevant stakeholders have interacted with this process throughout the project.

In line with Horizon Europe definitions, innovation is understood as the process and outcome by which new ideas respond to societal and economic needs, generating new or improved products, services, or organisational models that are successfully introduced into existing markets or capable of creating new ones, thereby delivering value to society. Innovation management is therefore the structured coordination of activities aimed at identifying, developing, and implementing new ideas, ensuring that they can be transformed into solutions that meet these needs.

Within SUSTRACK, partners were responsible for managing innovation-related activities linked to their results, with the support of the EM. These activities included: managing rights to use Background during and after the project; capturing and validating results; assessing, protecting, and managing intellectual property (IP); and ensuring that dissemination, exploitation, and deployment actions were effectively implemented.

Innovation management in SUSTRACK has encompassed two dimensions:

- **Innovation process management** - ensuring that mechanisms were in place to capture, protect, and exploit project results.
- **Change management** - enabling partners and stakeholders to adapt to and integrate new approaches, tools, and outputs.

To operationalise this, innovation management was embedded across the project lifecycle:

- Before and during implementation, the process ensured that access and use rights to Background IPs was clearly defined, and that project results were systematically captured, assessed, and protected.
- During the project execution, frameworks were established to ensure appropriate dissemination, exploitation, and communication measures, culminating in consolidated exploitation and dissemination plans.

The organisation of innovation management was led by PEDAL, as Task Leader for Task 6.4. The key activities carried out during SUSTRACK's implementation included:

- **Defining the innovation management plan** at the outset, ensuring that all processes were consistently applied across project activities, covering identification of IP rights, result validation, protection strategies, and dissemination/exploitation planning.
- **Liaising and communicating innovation management issues** through the Project Management Committee (PMC) and the Plenary Project Meetings.
- **Maintaining and validating the catalogue of project results**, ensuring accuracy and completeness of partner contributions.
- **Monitoring partner-level exploitation and dissemination plans** and ensuring their alignment with project objectives.
- **Supporting partners in identifying appropriate protection approaches (IPRs)** for project results, balancing openness with the need to secure value.

- **Guiding the consortium in defining the project’s most relevant contributions** to policy, industry, and society, thereby maximising SUSTRACK’s expected impacts.

Through this structured approach, innovation management in SUSTRACK has ensured that results were effectively captured, safeguarded, and positioned for long-term exploitation and sustainability.

8.1 Innovation and Sustainability Legacy

The SUSTRACK project has placed innovation and sustainability at the core of its exploitation strategy, ensuring that results are not only delivered but also positioned for long-term relevance and impact.

Innovation management within SUSTRACK has ensured that results were systematically identified, monitored, and matured throughout the project. This was achieved through the continuous use of the innovation management framework, the IPR Matrix, and the result catalogue. Dedicated activities—such as partner consultations, bilateral meetings, and innovation workshops—helped refine KERs, align them with stakeholder needs, and strengthen their readiness for exploitation. These practices created a culture of innovation management that extends beyond the formal end of the project.

In parallel, the sustainability strategy secures the continuation and accessibility of SUSTRACK’s outputs after the project’s conclusion. Key measures include:

The hosting of the SUSTRACK dashboard and the permanent archiving of project deliverables in open-access repositories (e.g., Zenodo), ensuring broad visibility and long-term accessibility:

- **Partner commitments to continue promoting and updating results**, in particular the Monitoring Tool, policy recommendations, and methodological guidelines, thereby maintaining their practical value.
- **Integration into EU networks and platforms**, such as the EU Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet), the EU Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform (ECESP), and industry alliances, which will continue to disseminate and mainstream SUSTRACK’s knowledge base.
- **Active exploration of continuation opportunities under Horizon Europe calls**, national initiatives, and future collaborative projects, aimed at further validating, replicating, and scaling SUSTRACK’s findings.

The long-term vision of SUSTRACK is to contribute systemically to Europe’s transition towards a sustainable circular bioeconomy. By embedding its outputs into European policy frameworks, industrial ecosystems, and research agendas, the project ensures that its legacy will endure beyond the funding period. This legacy is expressed not only in the specific tools and recommendations developed but also in the strengthened stakeholder networks, enhanced innovation capacity, and reinforced culture of collaboration created through SUSTRACK.

Through this combined approach, SUSTRACK leaves behind an innovation and sustainability legacy that is forward-looking, policy-relevant, and capable of supporting the ongoing systemic

transformation required under the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and related EU strategies.

8.2 Lessons learnt

The implementation of SUSTRACK project has provided valuable insights into the effective management of innovation, intellectual property rights (IPR), and exploitation strategies in Horizon Europe projects. These lessons are not only relevant for the consortium's future activities but also serve as guidance for other initiatives aiming to ensure sustainable exploitation of research results.

Early and Continuous IPR Alignment

Establishing clarity on Background and Foreground IPR from the outset and revisiting these agreements periodically helped prevent conflicts and ensured smooth progress. Importantly, no IPR disputes emerged during the project, demonstrating the effectiveness of this approach.

Exploitation as a Continuous Process

Rather than being treated as a one-off exercise, exploitation was embedded into the project lifecycle. The use of the Exploitation Assessment Template and structured bilateral discussions with partners enabled the early identification and progressive refinement of KERs.

Stakeholder Engagement as a Driver of Sustainability

Actively involving external stakeholders through policy dialogues, co-creation events, and industry platforms significantly increased the relevance and adoption potential of SUSTRACK results. The development of the Stakeholder Adoption Roadmap (Table 36) provided a practical tool to translate research outputs into tailored use cases.

Value of Dedicated Exploitation Management

The appointment of a dedicated EM proved critical for coordinating activities, facilitating partner discussions, and exploring external platforms (e.g. EU Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, EuBioNet, Innovation Radar) to ensure long-term visibility and uptake of results.

Balancing Protection and Dissemination

Partners learnt the importance of first securing appropriate protection for valuable results before dissemination. This balance ensured that project outcomes were both safeguarded and made widely available for maximum impact.

Integration into European Knowledge and Policy Ecosystems

Positioning SUSTRACK outputs within established EU platforms and networks guarantees long-term continuity and enhances the project's systemic contribution beyond its formal conclusion.

These lessons confirm that sustainable exploitation requires early planning, continuous monitoring, structured partner engagement, and proactive alignment with stakeholder needs and EU ecosystems. They provide a strong foundation not only for the legacy of Sustrack but also for improving exploitation strategies in future Horizon Europe and related initiatives.

9. STAKEHOLDER ADAPTION ROADMAP

The Stakeholder Adoption Roadmap positions SUSTRACK’s KERs as practical assets for diverse stakeholder groups, ensuring their continued use beyond the project’s lifetime. Its aim is to provide a clear and user-friendly entry point, enabling stakeholders to quickly identify the outputs most relevant to their needs and how these can be applied in practice. For policy makers at EU, national, and regional levels, KERs such as policy portfolio scenarios, recommendations, roadmap guidelines, the monitoring framework, and dashboard can inform evidence-based policy design, track progress towards the Green Deal and Fit for 55 targets and be integrated into regional planning processes. Industry and SMEs across construction, textiles, chemicals, plastics, and bio-based sectors can benefit from case study analyses, toolkits, and dashboard insights to benchmark practices, design sustainable business models, and align strategies with EU policy requirements. Academia and research organisations can integrate SUSTRACK case studies, methodological frameworks, reports, and event formats into curricula and research activities, while also replicating event formats in Horizon Europe projects to further promote stakeholder engagement.

Civil society, NGOs, and local communities can apply empowerment activities, co-creation event formats, and toolkits to conduct awareness campaigns, engage citizens in sustainability transitions, and mobilise grassroots contributions to circular and bio-based pathways. In parallel, EU platforms and networks such as EuBioNet and the Circular Bioeconomy Cluster play a vital role in ensuring the long-term visibility of SUSTRACK’s outputs by hosting them in open repositories, promoting replication of event formats and toolkits across EU-funded projects, and maintaining the dashboard as a shared EU resource. To support accessibility and reuse, all public SUSTRACK results are archived in the SUSTRACK website, partner repositories, and on a dedicated Zenodo community profile for the project. Stakeholders are encouraged to adapt and integrate SUSTRACK results into their own initiatives, with the support of partner institutions where needed. A consolidated overview of these adoption pathways, relevant KERs, and expected impacts is presented in Table 35. As such, the roadmap serves as a living guide for future projects and initiatives, ensuring the sustained legacy and systemic impact of SUSTRACK’s results well beyond the project’s conclusion.

Table 35 below links SUSTRACK’s KERs to relevant stakeholder groups, highlighting adoption pathways and the expected impact beyond the project’s lifetime.

Table 35 Stakeholder Adaptation Roadmap

Stakeholder Groups	Relevant KERs	Adoption Pathways	Expected Impact
Policy Makers (EU, national, regional)	Policy Portfolio Scenarios; Policy Recommendations; Monitoring & Assessment Framework; Dashboard	Inform policy design and roadmaps; apply monitoring framework; integrate tools into regional and national planning	Evidence-based policy development; alignment with EU Green Deal and Fit for 55 targets
Industry & SMEs (construction, textiles, chemicals, plastics, bio-based sectors)	Case Study Analyses; Toolkits; Dashboard	Benchmark practices; apply toolkits for sustainable business models; use dashboard for reporting and strategy alignment	Improved sectoral practices; enhanced competitiveness through sustainability and compliance with EU policy
Academia & Research Organisations	Case Studies; Reports & Deliverables; Monitoring Framework; Event Formats	Integrate case studies into curricula; extend methodological frameworks; replicate event formats in new projects	Capacity-building for future researchers; strengthened methodological base for sustainability transitions
Civil Society, NGOs & Local Communities	Stakeholder Empowerment Activities; Co-Creation Event Formats; Toolkits	Apply training formats in campaigns; engage citizens in co-creation; use toolkits for grassroots initiatives	Greater citizen awareness; active civil society participation in sustainability transitions
EU Platforms & Networks (e.g. EuBioNet, Circular Bioeconomy Cluster)	Policy Recommendations; Event Format Package; Toolkits; Dashboard	Host outputs in open repositories; replicate event formats; maintain dashboard as shared EU resource	Long-term visibility; replication across EU projects; sustained contribution to EU knowledge base

10. CONCLUSIONS AND WAY FORWARD

The Final Exploitation and Sustainability Plan consolidates the collective efforts of the SUSTRACK consortium to ensure that the project's results are effectively protected, exploited, and sustained beyond the project's formal duration. Through a robust intellectual property rights (IPR) framework, a comprehensive IPR Matrix, and a structured innovation management process, the consortium has been able to identify, validate, and position its Key Exploitable Results (KERs) for long-term use and impact. Importantly, no IPR conflicts emerged during implementation, underscoring the clarity of the agreements in place and the cooperative spirit of the partnership.

The plan demonstrates that SUSTRACK's results extend far beyond academic deliverables: they represent practical assets with clear application routes for policy makers, industry, academia, civil society, and EU networks. By embedding its outputs in European and national policy processes, industry practices, and stakeholder engagement frameworks, SUSTRACK strengthens Europe's transition towards a circular bioeconomy in line with the European Green Deal, the Circular Economy Action Plan, and related EU strategies.

Looking forward, the consortium has committed to several measures that will secure the continuity of SUSTRACK's legacy. Public results will remain permanently accessible through the dedicated Zenodo community profile, the SUSTRACK website and partner repositories. The Monitoring and Assessment Framework and Dashboard will be further promoted via EU platforms such as the Circular Economy Stakeholder Platform, ensuring visibility and uptake. In addition, targeted dissemination and exploitation activities—ranging from publication in open repositories to engagement with industry alliances—will continue to support the adoption of results.

The way forward lies in leveraging SUSTRACK's assets in future European and national initiatives, particularly within the Horizon Europe framework, where the methodological approaches, monitoring tools, and stakeholder engagement formats developed in the project can be replicated and expanded. The consortium's commitment to promoting, updating, and integrating results into wider networks ensures that SUSTRACK will leave a lasting legacy as both a knowledge base and a practical enabler of systemic change.

Project Consortium

11. ANNEXES

Annex 1 - SUSTRACK's Identified IP BG

No.	Relevant BG	Contributing Partner	BG Number	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Conditions to use outside SUSTRACK	Interest in further exploitation through SUSTRACK results
1	“European Bioeconomy Network” database and mailing lists	FVA	BG1	“European Bioeconomy Network” database and mailing lists	Copyright	Was used for project activities by FVA, but will not be shared among partners	Was used for project’s activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
2	“European Bioeconomy Network” website, knowledge and partnership	FVA	BG2	“European Bioeconomy Network” website, knowledge and partnership	None	Was used for project activities by FVA	Was used for project’s activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
3	Biovoices social media	FVA	BG3	Biovoices social media channels	None	Was not directly used by the project, but can be deployed for joint activities and initiatives with BIOGov.net social media channels	Was used by FVA, but will not be subject to exploitation by the consortium	N/A

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4	BioArt Gallery	FVA	BG4	The BIOArt Gallery is a collection of stunning pictures of the most promising feedstock and its related bioeconomy applications in everyday life. It offers an innovative approach to showcasing to the public some examples of bio-based products and applications currently available in the market through several examples: cosmetics, nutraceuticals, tissues, toys and sports, disposable tableware, cleaning products, gadgets, and much more.	Copyright	Was used for project activities by FVA	Was used for project's activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
5	Bioeconomy Village	FVA	BG5	The Bioeconomy Village is a collection of more than 350 bio-based products and aims at raising public awareness, improving knowledge on bio-based products and promoting the applications and benefits of the circular bioeconomy and sustainability, encouraging dialogue, discussion and sharing between the general public and representatives of universities, research centres, projects, companies, associations and start-ups.	None	Was used for project activities by FVA	Was used for project's activities by FVA, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
6	FVA Database of contacts in the	FVA	BG6	FVA Database of contacts in the bioeconomy sector	None	Was used by FVA for the project's activities, but	Was used for project's activities by FVA,	N/A

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	bioeconomy sector					not shared with the partners	but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	
7	Methodology to quantify soil impacts	CIRCE	BG7	Methodology to quantify the global agricultural crop footprint including soil impacts	None	Was owned and used exclusively by CIRCE for Task 2.2.	Developed by CIRCE before starting of SUSTRACK project. It was owned and used exclusively by CIRCE for exploiting the results.	Yes
8	Methodology and model for analysing the cross-sectoral impacts of policy	KE	BG8	The Green Economy Model (GEM) is a System Dynamics based model that was developed to analyse the cross-sectoral impacts of green development strategies. It allows for simulating the cross-sectoral impacts of policy interventions and thereby enables a more systemic assessment of the sustainability of specific policies/policy packages as well as related costs, avoided costs and added benefits.	None	Was used for project activities by KE	Was used for the project's activities by KE, but will not be subject to further exploitation by the consortium	N/A
9	Methodology to develop portfolio policy scenarios based on a template	DBFZ	BG9	Methodology to develop policy portfolio scenarios. It will contain a template, including policies relevant to the transition from a linear and fossil-based economy	None	Was used for project activities by DBFZ	Free to use	No

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				towards a circular and bio-based one. The template will be filled out via partners and will be applied in the GEM.				
10	Policies for technology transfer	DBFZ	BG10	There is an institutional internal policy for technology transfer	None	Was the baseline for the institutional internal work but followed within the project's activities but not usable/shareable within the SUSTRACK Project	Not usable outside DBFZ or SUSTRACK	No
11	Drop-in database on biomass potentials from abandoned and degraded lands; on marginal land availability in EU27	WR	BG11	Data at regional level on biomass availability from abandoned and degraded lands towards 2030, 2050; Data at regional level on marginal land availability in EU27	None	Was used as input in the GEM model	Was used for project's activities in WP4, but will not be subject of further exploitation by the consortium	No

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Annex 2 - SUSTRACK's Identified IP FG

WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
	1.1	Report on the literature gaps and trade-offs	-	UNIT	KE, UNIFE, BAM, TECNALIA, UGENT	-	This public report provides an overview of the work conducted within Task 1.1. Specifically, it will present findings obtained by reviewing and analysing existing literature and recent EU surveys on trends with respect to the environmental, economic and social limits of the linear, carbon-intensive, and fossil-based economy.	FG1.1	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
1	1.3	Report on the prioritisation of the identified limits, as well as the preliminary guidelines and policy recommendations	-	UNIT	CIRCE, BAM, TECNALIA, UNIFE, PC, DBFZ, KE,WR,	-	This public report provides an overview of the work conducted within Task 1.3. Specifically, it presents previously identified limits that are prioritized through pairwise comparisons based on expert judgements.	FG1.3	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
1	1.4	Report on the literature gaps and trade-offs	The full list of identified barriers to the transition in the construction, chemicals, plastics, and textile	UNIT	KE, UNIFE, BAM, TECNALIA, UGENT	-	This public report provides an overview of the work conducted within Task 1.1. Specifically, it presents findings obtained by reviewing and analysing existing literature and recent EU surveys on trends with respects to the environmental, economic and social limits of the linear, carbon-	FG1.1	none	Free to use	no	Free to use

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WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
			sectors under cultural, economic, environmental, governance, structural, and technical dimensions.				intensive, and fossil-based economy.					
2	2.1	System of monitor and assessment of the benefits of the sustainable transition	#1- monitoring and assessment framework #2 - monitoring and assessment dashboard	TECNALIA	FVA, DBFZ, BAM, UNIT, WR, KE, PC, CIRCE	BG7 (CIRCE)	Framework and dashboard for decision makers to monitor and assess circularity and the sustainability impacts of the transition at different levels	FG2.1	Creative Common Licence	Free to use	No	Free to use
2	2.2	Improving knowledge for assessing specific aspects of the sustainable transition	#1- monitoring and assessment framework #2 - monitoring and	WR	CIRCE, FVA, DBFZ, KE, TEC, UNIT	-	(a) the development of methods to evaluate soil quality and other land-use impacts; (b) the linking of micro-and macro-modelling approaches (e.g., life cycle assessment of circularity, environmental and socio-economic impacts for key sectors, economy-wide assessment of	FG2.2	Creative Common Licence	Free to use	No	Free to use

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WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
			assessment dashboard				material flows, national/regional assessment of the environment, society, and economy); and (c) the quantification of monetisation factors to estimate externalities related to environmental and social impacts and the monetary value of ecosystem service flows.					
2	2.3	Advancement of sustainability assessment knowledge: final	#1- monitoring and assessment framework #2 monitoring and assessment dashboard	WR	CIRCE, FVA, DBFZ, KE, TEC, UNIT	-	This public report is an update of Deliverable 2.2 taking account of all insights derived during the project, particularly in the testing of new indicators and metrics in the case studies performed in WP3.	FG2.3	Creative Common License	Free to use	No	Free to use
2	2.4	Analysis and development of sustainability thresholds	Sustainability thresholds defined for some indicators	BAM	TEC, UNIT, WR, DBFZ, FVA, KE, UNIFE, PEDAL, UGENT	-	This public report identifies and proposes, when possible, thresholds for the indicators to be included in the framework to monitor and assess the benefits of the sustainable transition. The identification of thresholds are done by conducting desk research complemented by different interactions with stakeholders.	FG2.5	None	Free to use	No	Free to use

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WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
3	3.4	Overall findings, recommendations and conclusions from case studies	#3 To assess the environmental, social and economic impacts of the sustainable transition, with regard to selected case studies.	WR	UGENT, UNIT, CIRCE, PC, KE, TEC, DBFZ, BAM	-	The results of the case studies were generalised to provide conclusions and recommendations for the four bio-based sectors.	FG3.4	Creative Common Licence	Free to use	No	Free to use
4	4.1	Report presenting scenarios and related policy packages	- Template for collecting policy instruments - Collection of policy instruments - Generated scenarios for each case study	DBFZ	UNIT, BAM, WR, TEC, KE, UNIFE, PEDAL, UGENT	BG9/BG10	The methodological background of the scenario development is differentiated within different steps and deliverables. 1. Development of a template to collect policy instruments related to the case studies 2. Evaluation of the collected policy tools and analysis of the status quo of policy tools already in force (baseline scenario) 3. Development of sustainable BE scenarios in cooperation with other work packages for each case study 4. Report about the methodology used and information collected about policy tools.	FG4.1	Creative Common Licence	Free to use	No	Free to use

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WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
4	4.3	Report presenting the results of all simulations and documentation of the model	a. Description of scenarios b. Comparison of scenarios c. Analysis of cross-sectoral policy impacts in the transitioning scenarios d. Insight into the impact of policy, including investment requirements, avoided costs and added benefits resulting from the transition	KE	-	-	The report presents the simulations that were used to assess the systemic impacts of policies aiming to facilitate the transition toward a sustainable bioeconomy. Documentation of the model was provided to ensure that the reader understands the methodological foundations used to generate the results.	FG4.3	None	Free to use	No	Free to use
5	5.1	Final policy brief: policy priorities to	#5. To identify	WR	UNIT, DBFZ, CIRCE, PEDAL,		This public report presents the policy priorities to support the	FG5.2	None	Free to use	No	Free to use

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WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
		support the sustainable transition and examples of good policies	policy priorities, define corresponding policy actions and provide recommendations to policy makers		FVA, KE, BAM, TEC	-	sustainable transition to a circular bioeconomy with a focus on EU policy instruments and instruments available at the national and regional levels. It makes recommendations for good policy examples. The derived policy priorities and examples of good policies will be based on a systematic review of policy instruments and a validation process with stakeholders in co-creation workshops that took place at the INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences of SUSTRACK.					
6	6.1	Identity	website, brand, logo, social media, promotional video and video teasers, factsheets, infographic cards, dashboard	FVA	All partners	-	The SUSTRACK brand enhanced throughout the duration of the project facilitating the dissemination and exploitation of the project's outcome	FG5.6	Copyright	Free to use	No	Free to use

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WP	PR number	Project Result (PR) /Achievement	Specific Project Result	Main Contributing Partner(s)	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Short Description of FG	Foreground Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within SUSTRACK	Interest in Further Commercialisation of SUSTRACK Results	Conditions to Use after the end of the Project
			visual identity									
6	6.2-6.3	Event format package	Innovative co-creation workshops, policy roundtables, capacity building	FVA	All partners	BG1, BG2, BG6	Innovative formats (live, online, hybrid) of collaboration and stakeholder engagement with enhanced gamified applications and tools, in the context of INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT and DEPLOY conferences as well as MML.	FG5.7	Copyright	Free to use	No	Free to use
6	6.1	Toolkits	Deployment package of SUSTRACK toolkits	FVA	All partners	-	Combination of all knowledge assets with explanations produced by the project and useful for their replication and exploitation	FG5.8	Copyright	Free to use	No	Free to use